

Evaluation of Multi-Quality Parameter Fluctuations in Smelting Anodes for Furnace Oil-Fired Anode Baking Furnaces

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Abstract: In the aluminium Industry, carbon anode is the most significant component for electrolytic cells in primary aluminium production. Commercially, it reduces the total cost of Aluminium production by 15%, and for inferior quality, it may go up 25% [1]. Carbon consumption in electrolytic cells varies from 400 kg/Mt of Al produced to 450 kg/Mt which is affected by CO reactivity residue (CRR) and air reactivity residue (ARR) of anodes [2, 3, 4]. The Anode reactivity is affected by the properties of raw materials as poor-quality green anodes cannot be converted into high-quality baked anodes. However, the level of the baking procedure and parameters decide the reactivity of anodes, which are to be used for electrolysis. Low and high baking results in higher reactivity whereas optimum baking results in the lowest anode reactivity as well as the lowest consumption [5]. Baking of anodes takes place in Baking Furnace where important parameters are fire cycle, fire temperature, and soaking time [6, 7]. However, with a lower fire cycle also fire temperature can be achieved but it will lead to high energy consumption and reduced quality of anodes [8]. Actual density and resistivity are other parameters to be checked for anode quality.

The present study is limited to a variation of ARR, CRR, real density, and resistivity with varying heating temperature and soaking time in the furnace to obtain optimum parameters to get good quality baked anodes. Parameters of anode manufacturing were observed for twenty-four months with three latest arts of the technologies and data obtained from baking furnaces were analyzed, with varying inputs and output data as well as its impact in electrolysis for carbon consumption. Mathematical models and Graphs were plotted on a real-time basis to establish the relationship among the parameters and its impact on quality [9].

It was observed that higher values of carbon reactivity residue and oxygen reactivity residue improve the quality of anodes and the optimum value of real density is obtained. Lower values of CRR and ARR result in dusting whereas higher values of CRR and ARR develop cracks. Suitable combinations help in lowering the level of anode consumption in the electrolysis process of Smelter Pots [10, 11]. CRR >95%, ARR >90%, It was further observed that Baked Anode density from 1.60 to 1.605 and Resistivity < 55 M Ohm are the most suitable parameters for smelter-grade Anodes.

Keywords: ARR, CRR, Real density, Resistivity, Aluminium electrolytic cell, soaking time, soaking temperature.

1.1 Introduction

In Hall-Héroult electrolysis pot for primary aluminium production, carbon anodes are consumed, with net carbon consumption serving as a key measure of anode performance [12]. Theoretically, consumption is 334 kg/C/MT Al, but practical use ranges from 400–450 kg/C/Mt Al due to losses from current inefficiency, secondary air reactions, and anode quality issues. The carbon requirement follows this reaction [12]:

Electrolysis Reaction:

2 molecules of Alumina + 3 atoms of carbon → 4 atoms of Aluminium + 3 molecules of carbon dioxide i.e.,
 $2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3\text{C} + \text{Electrical energy} \rightarrow 4\text{Al} + 3\text{CO}_2$

In terms of Masses of the different elements are as follows:

Mass Breakdown:

1 mole Al = 27 g → Al₂O₃ = 102 g

1 mole C = 12 g → CO₂ = 44 g

1 mole O = 16 g

In terms of masses, the reaction is formulated:

To produce 1 tonne of Aluminium, the requirement is as follows:

$$36/108 = 0.333 \text{ tonne of carbon}$$

$$\text{And as an indication: } 204/108 = 1.88 \text{ tonne of Alumina}$$

1.2 Net Carbon Consumption Formula [13]:

$$NC = C + (334/CE) + 1.2 (BT-960) - 1.7 CRR + 9.3 AP + 8 TC - 1.5 ARR \text{ (R\&D Carbon)}$$

CRR drops by 8–10%, it increases anode consumption by 12–20 kg/C/MT Al, with similar effects seen from ARR variations. If both fall short by 10%, consumption rises by 25–40 kg/C/t Al. Poor-quality anodes generate 10% more CO₂ and significantly more CF₄, raising production costs by \$40 million annually for a 360,000 TPA smelter.

1.3 Green Anodes from GAP (Green Anode Plant)

Green anodes from GAP are baked for mechanical, thermal, and electrical optimization before use in smelters [3, 9]. They are treated in Anode Baking Furnaces using flame burner, offering efficient heat transfer but causing inconsistent heat flux, which affects properties like resistivity, air and CO₂ reactivity, and density. Critical operational factors include baking temperature, soaking temperature, flue temperature, and fire movement [14]. Despite modern automation, maintaining consistent anode quality remains challenging over extended operations of up to 36 months [15]. Cost-saving measures without proper research often degrade anode quality [16, 17]

1.4 A pictorial view of the furnace for actual operations such as anode loading, various furnace components, and fire movement for heat treatment of the Green Anodes is shown in Figs. 1(a) to 1(c).

Fig. 1 (a), Actual Anode Baking Furnace of Modern Aluminium Smelter

Fig.1 (b) Open Ring Baking Furnace

Fig. 1 (c), Fire directions (Preheating, Heating, Blowing, and Cooling Zone) [5],

- Sections 1 to 3: Preheating,
- Sections 4 to 6: Heating,
- Sections 7 to 10: Blowing,
- Sections: 11 to 13: Cooling,
- Sections 14 to 17: Unpacking, maintenance & Packing)

Fig. 1(a) illustrates a large Anode Baking Furnace, known as a ring furnace due to its structure [18], where green anodes are baked. Two primary designs are used in the aluminum industry: open-top (horizontal flue) and closed-top (vertical flue) furnaces. These high-temperature heat exchangers use indirect heating from the combustion of natural gas [19], furnace oil, or LDO (Light Diesel Oil). This study focuses exclusively on furnace oil heating.

The furnace typically consists of 34 to 70 sections (two to four fire groups) arranged in parallel rows with crossovers [20]. Each section, or chamber, contains four to eight parallel pits enclosed by two flues [Figs. 1 & 2], where anode blocks are placed and surrounded by filler coke [Fig. 1(b)] to prevent oxidation and ensure heat transfer [21, 22]. Recently, filler coke with plastic covering has gained popularity to minimize air ingress, enhancing energy conservation and uniform heat distribution [23].

Thermocouples are strategically placed to monitor temperature consistency across layers and anodes. After each firing cycle, burner ramps, exhaust, and cooling manifolds advance to the next section following the flue gas flow [Fig. 1(c)]. Anode temperatures can reach 1050°C–1200°C as burners approach [24].

The firing process involves three preheating sections, three firing sections, and four to six cooling sections [Fig. 1(c)]. The movement of fire equipment follows the fire’s progression, which dictates production rates and ensures the desired anode quality.

1.5: This research relies on the data of more than thousands in numbers of live Anode baking furnaces, without introducing new prototype models, using ABF CFD modeling to analyze furnace pressure, temperature profiles, flue movement, heat input, and dissipation with high precision [25].

2 nd Thermal Exchanger Gas → Solids	1 st Thermal Exchanger Solids → Gas
Negative Pressure Zone	Positive pressure Zone

- TA: Anode Temperature profile during a complete cycle.
- TG: Gas Temperature profile during a complete cycle.
- TG – TA: Thermal gradient gas/ Anode

Fig. 2 (a), Anode temperature & Flue Gas Temperature change during the operation cycle of Anode Baking Furnace (Reid Hammer Germany)

Fig. 2 (b) Plot based on actual gas temperature variations in the furnace for baking of Anodes.

The study examines heating cycles and baking temperatures in an anode baking furnace (ABF), highlighting key processes across temperature gradients. Graph 2(a), produced in the Reid & Hammer laboratory and ABF supplier

and Fig. 2(b), a live operational graph, illustrate the stages of baking and corresponding changes in anode behavior [26].

1. 0–200 °C: Initial thermal expansion of the binder pitch occurs, relieving internal tension and slightly reducing density, which weakens aggregate interlocking.
2. 200–350 °C: Pitch redistributes into voids, promoting aggregate post-impregnation and influencing stub hole slumping, permeability, mechanical strength, and resistivity.
3. 350–450 °C: Light volatiles are released, accompanied by a minor reduction in anode density.
4. 450–600 °C: Green anodes undergo coking; thermal gradients induce microcracks, relieving internal stress.
5. 600–900 °C: Post-coking processes release residual volatiles and initiate annealing, with negligible effects on key parameters.
6. 900–1200 °C: Crystalline growth occurs, with contraction-induced tension arising from prior calcination stages.

Literature Survey:

Zhang et al. investigated heat transfer simulation in horizontal anode baking furnaces, revealing that reducing cycle time lowered fuel consumption, with airflow reduction and air filtration optimization contributing to fuel efficiency [2]. Thor et al. (2010) analyzed furnace temperature dependency on CO and CO₂ concentrations, dominated by methane, though energy consumption and quality correlations were inconclusive [23].

Felix et al. (2010) identified multiple factors influencing specific energy consumption beyond process control, including pit dimensions, pitch content, flue length, production rate, false air, operational practices, baking temperature, and furnace sections [18]. However, their study did not prioritize the most influential parameters. Marina et al. proposed an innovative flue top block design, that enhances energy efficiency, process control, and refractory lifespan [33].

Dagoberto et al. (2011) examined furnace design improvements for performance optimization but omitted heat flux and temperature profiles crucial for quality control [15]. Linhares et al. (2020) suggested quality improvements through energy reduction, overlooking waste heat recovery, which directly affects energy efficiency and product quality [34].

Borzu et al. (2013) discussed key parameters for furnace design selection but lacked focus on quality-related outcomes [9]. Tajik et al. (2020) explored energy-saving controls in ABF but did not address the quality implications of reduced energy consumption [35].

Werner et al. (2013) analyzed baking parameters such as heat rate, temperature, and soaking time in relation to anode behavior during electrolysis [31]. Liu et al. (2016) emphasized achieving homogeneous anode quality and reducing oil consumption through numerical simulations, though practical scalability from lab to industrial settings remained challenging [22].

Yasmine et al. (2016) highlighted the influence of heating rates on carbon anode properties for aluminum production, linking baking conditions to electrolysis behavior [1]. Abdul et al. (2017) found that longer fire cycle, soaking time, and temperature improved homogeneity but reduced production volume, without addressing anode property impacts [20].

2.1 Research Gap

1. Anode quality uniformity has received limited attention in the existing research, which primarily concentrates on average parameters of baked anode quality. Ensuring uniform quality demands a consistent distribution of heat flux and the implementation of a precise, robust temperature measurement system.
2. Although quality parameters of baked anodes have been extensively examined, previous investigations were constrained by limited sample sizes and sub-optimal baking temperatures. Consequently, a significant portion of the data was extrapolated beyond empirically measured values, potentially compromising reliability.

3. Achieving industrial-scale baking temperatures in laboratory environments has been deemed economically unfeasible. As a result, data extrapolation beyond specific thermal thresholds was conducted without fully accounting for practical operational constraints.
4. Earlier research predominantly emphasized mean values for anode quality assessment, which, despite appearing sufficient, can present a misleading evaluation. Incorporating both maximum and minimum values is essential, as the presence of a single defective anode within a set of 32 can disrupt electrolysis stability, resulting in substantial economic losses.

3.0 Procedures for experimental work:

(a) Baked Anode – Sample preparation

As the finished product baked anode sample received (length-350 mm)

Fig. 3 (a) Sample preparation

(b) Various steps for sample preparation:

4.1 Sample Cutting:

- 20 mm- for Ash, Crystallization value (LC), Real density, and chemical analysis.
 - 60 mm- for Air reactivity and CO₂ reactivity
 - 140 mm- for Electrical resistivity and Apparent density
 - 50 mm- for Air permeability
2. **Drying: Sample dried at 110 °C for 12hrs.**

Fig. 3 (b), Prepared Samples

3. **Drilling- for Air reactivity. (To the depth of 30mm)**
4. **Chemical Analysis- By XRF (X-Ray Florescence) method.**
5. **Physical Parameters**
 - Ash
 - LC (Crystallization value)
 - Real density- XRD
 - Apparent density
 - Electrical resistivity
 - CO₂ reactivity
 - Air reactivity
 - Air permeability

Real Density, Electrical Resistivity, CO₂ reactivity, and air reactivity were considered for experiments and study

Equipment Name	Equipment	Parameter
XRD		Real Density
Resistivity meter		Electrical Resistivity
Air Reactivity meter		Air Reactivity Residue
CO ₂ Reactivity meter		CO ₂ reactivity residue

Fig. 4, Photographs of Testing Instrument

4.0 Experimental Observations

4.1 Sample Laboratory Data collection report for each day for the entire 365 days [27]:

Table 1 Experimental Results

Analysis	parameter	units	Sample receiving date	01-Apr-21	01-Apr-21	01-Apr-21	01-Apr-21	01-Apr-21	01-Apr-21	02-Apr-21
			Report sent date	02-Apr-21						
			Sample Id	S54-P1-L1-1039A0107	S54-P5-L3-1072B0283	S06-P1-L1-1072B0263	S06-P5-L3-1072A0299	S38-P1-L1-1071B0076	S38-P5-L3-1072B0049	S55-P1-L1-1072B0189
Physical analysis	Real Density	gm/cc	-	2.083	2.093	2.088	2.093	2.094	2.092	2.082
	Crystallization value (Lc)	A°	30 min.	30.88	33.2	31.91	33.08	33.47	32.98	30.74
	Geometric density	gm/cc	≥ 1.58	1.595	1.586	1.586	1.586	1.583	1.572	1.586
	Electrical Resistivity	μΩ m	<57	58.63	56.23	59.58	57.02	58.45	56.49	58.81

	Air permeability	N perm	<1.2							
	Air Reactivity Dust	%	<6	7.9		7.6		5.7		7.7
	Air Reactivity Residue	%	>78	70.3		68.2		65.8		75.3
	Air Reactivity loss	%	-	21.8		24.2		28.5		17.0
	Carboxy Reactivity Dust	%	<6	5.1	1.0	5.5	2.5	2.8	2.4	1.9
	Carboxy Reactivity Residue	%	>84	87.2	92.8	86.1	90.3	90.4	91.4	90.9
	Carboxy Reactivity loss	%	-	7.7	6.2	8.4	7.2	6.8	6.2	7.2

The evaluation and real-time analysis of operational parameters affecting furnace performance through laboratory tests typically represent a limited investigation and do not accurately reflect the practical dynamics of the baking process. Consequently, long-term data collection from an operational furnace, incorporating automation and mathematical modeling, is essential for analyzing the influence of various parameters on anode quality. The identified gap in furnace operations, despite access to advanced analytical technologies and skilled engineers, arises from an absence of both micro- and macro-level perspectives. Even with modern advancements, industries still experience significant revenue losses due to suboptimal operational efficiency. Table 1 presents sample data from the Anode Baking Furnace an Art of the technology Aluminium Smelter Data collection involved four samples per parameter daily over 365 days, resulting in 1,460 samples per parameter and 5,840 total samples across four parameters. This extensive dataset facilitates a comprehensive analysis of furnace performance to optimize operational parameters [28].

Table 2 Temp. Vs quality parameters

Flue Temperature vs. carbon anode Temperature and quality parameters (ARR, CRR, Bulk density & Resistivity) {29}											
Month	Final Flue Temp Per °C	Final Anode Temp (Max) °C	Final Anode Temp (Min) °C	ARR (Min)	CRR (Min)	CRR (Max)	Bulk Density (Min)	Bulk Density (Max)	Resistivity (Min)	Resistivity (Max)	Resistivity (Min)
Nov-21	1175	1137	1092	60.8	72.5	84.6	92.1	1.56	1.6	58	62.5
Dec-21	1175	1142	1134	60.9	70.8	87.9	91.3	1.57	1.61	56.4	66.1
Jan-22	1180	1139	1134	64.2	68.7	88	93.8	1.56	1.59	56.6	67.6
Feb-22	1180	1137	1112	61	67.6	89.9	95	1.561	1.6	56	61.3
Mar-22	1180	1142	1132	57.7	68.1	90.6	95.3	1.573	1.614	52.7	61.2
Apr-22	1178	1137	1135	60.2	66.4	89	93.6	1.552	1.584	55.3	65.1
May-22	1179	1137	1116	69.5	80	91.1	95.7	1.573	1.599	57.7	65.5
Jun-22	1158	1136	1083	66	77.4	93.5	97.9	1.558	1.589	60.1	65.1
Jul-22	1171	1131	1128	70.2	77.5	89.5	94.5	1.561	1.607	59.9	66.4
Aug-22	1173	1134	1128	72.7	77.5	90.8	96.4	1.525	1.59657	57	70.5
Sep-22	1171	1134	1089	67.3	74.7	90.1	95.3	1.555	1.601	52	65
Oct-22	1171	1135	1090	63.6	77	90	94	1.572	1.607	57.5	62.9
Nov-22	1171	1135	1122	66.5	73.3	90.8	93.4	1.547	1.599	55.1	67.2
Dec-22	1180	1142	1129	70	79.7	90	94.2	1.565	1.597	55.9	64.3

In Table 2, the dataset is structured without incorporating mean values, as averages can be misleading by presenting overly favorable results, potentially providing production managers with a false sense of operational efficiency. The furnace flue temperature remains relatively stable throughout the data collection period, potentially due to increased FO/LDO (fuel oil/light diesel oil) input. However, the corresponding anode temperature exhibits significant variability, ranging from 1089 °C to 1142 °C of 53 °C deviation, where a narrower range is preferable.

Key performance indicators reveal notable fluctuations: ARR ranges from 57.5 to 80.0 (where higher values are preferable), CRR spans from 84.6 to 97 (higher values are also favorable), bulk density varies from 1.552 to 1.614 g/cm³ (higher values indicate better quality), and resistivity fluctuates between 52 and 66.4 μΩ·cm (lower values are preferable). Despite maintaining the flue temperature within 1175–1180 °C, these variations suggest a lack of effective control over furnace parameters.

Additionally, attempts to elevate anode temperature by adjusting flue settings failed to achieve stabilization within a desirable standard deviation range of 10–15 °C.

Table 3 further illustrates the correlation between temperature fluctuations and individual parameter variations.

Table 3. Differential Anode Temp vs. Differential Anode Bulk Density

Month	Final Anode Temp(max) °C	Final Anode Temp (Min) °C	Bulk Density unit (Min)	Bulk Density unit (Max)	Diff Temp(°C)	Diff Bulk Density*100 (**)
Nov-21	1137	1092	1.56	1.6	45	4
Dec-21	1142	1134	1.57	1.61	8	4
Jan-22	1139	1134	1.56	1.59	5	3
Feb-22	1137	1112	1.561	1.6	25	3.9
Mar-22	1142	1132	1.573	1.614	10	4.1
Apr-22	1137	1135	1.552	1.584	2	3.2
May-22	1137	1116	1.573	1.599	21	2.6
Jun-22	1136	1083	1.558	1.589	53	3.1
July-22	1131	1128	1.561	1.607	3	4.6
Aug-22	1134	1128	1.525	1.596	6	7.1
Sep-22	1134	1089	1.555	1.601	45	4.6
Oct	1135	1090	1.572	1.607	45	3.5
Nov-22	1135	1122	1.547	1.599	13	5.2
Dec-22	1142	1129	1.565	1.597	13	3.2

**** Multiplied by 100 to see clear variation in the graph and no significance in mathematical calculations.**

Fig. 5 (a) Plot between Temperature and Bulk density

Fig. 5 (b) Plot between Temperature difference and Bulk density difference

Table 3 presents a reorganization of data related to the high and low-temperature ranges of anodes, the range of baked anode temperatures, and corresponding bulk density values. The graph plotted with baked temperature on the Y-axis and bulk density on the X-axis [Fig. 6(b)] indicates stable operational conditions, suggesting no cause for concern. However, analysis of [Fig. 6(a)], which plots differential temperature on the Y-axis against bulk density on the X-axis, reveals irregular temperature variations without a discernible pattern. Ideally, bulk density should inversely correlate with temperature variation—lower temperature differentials should correspond to minimal fluctuations in bulk density.

The absence of this expected pattern likely arises from focusing on underbaked anodes that have not reached the target baking temperature. Despite maintaining anode temperatures within the 1080–1100 °C range, a significant portion of the data indicates low bulk density, implying underbaking. Accurate temperature measurements are critical; no anodes should fall below 1080 °C, as this threshold reflects optimal furnace performance when measured accurately [29].

4.2 Temp and Resistivity

Table 4 Observation of Temperature vs. Resistivity

Month	Final Anode Temp (Max)- °C	Final Anode Temp (Min)- °C	Resistivity (Min)	Resistivity (Max)	Diff. Temp	Diff. ins Resistivity
Nov-21	1137	1092	58	62.5	45	4.5
Dec-21	1142	1134	56.4	66.1	8	9.7
Jan-22	1139	1134	56.6	67.6	5	11
Feb-22	1137	1112	56	61.3	25	5.3
Mar-22	1142	1132	52.7	61.2	10	8.5
Apr-22	1137	1135	55.3	65.1	2	9.8
May-22	1137	1116	57.7	65.5	21	7.8
Jun-22	1136	1083	60.1	65.1	53	5
Jul-22	1131	1128	59.9	66.4	3	6.5
Aug-22	1134	1128	57	70.5	6	13.5
Sep-22	1134	1089	52	65	45	13
Oct-22	1135	1090	57.5	62.9	45	5.4
Nov-22	1135	1122	55.1	67.2	13	12.1
Dec-22	1142	1129	55.9	64.3	13	8.4

Fig. 6 (a) Plot between Temperature and Resistivity Fig. 6 (b) Diff. in Temp between Diff. in Resistivity

Table 3 and Figures 5(a) and 5(b) present comparable data, previously discussed concerning the real density of baked anodes. Anode resistivity influences the voltage drop significantly, directly affecting aluminum production efficiency. Lower resistivity is preferred, with an optimal threshold of 55 or below; however, in this case, it reaches 67.6. In a 360-kA pot, each unit increase in resistivity raises energy consumption by approximately 1.3 mV/MT [30]. Analyzing under-baked anodes, particularly those processed below 1080°C, is more beneficial than relying on industry-average values for enhancing operational efficiency.

4.3 Temperature and CRR

Table 5 Observation of Temperature vs. CRR

Month	Final Anode Temp (Max) °C	Final Anode Temp (Min)- °C	CRR (Min)	CRR (Max)	Diff. in Temp (°C)	Differential CRR
Nov-21	1137	1092	84.6	92.1	45	7.5
Dec-21	1142	1134	87.9	91.3	8	3.4
Jan-22	1139	1134	88	93.8	5	5.8
Feb-22	1137	1112	89.9	95	25	5.1
Mar-22	1142	1132	90.6	95.3	10	4.7
Apr-22	1137	1135	89	93.6	2	4.6
May-22	1137	1116	91.1	95.7	21	4.6
Jun-22	1136	1083	93.5	97.9	53	4.4
July-22	1131	1128	89.5	94.5	3	5
Aug-22	1134	1128	90.8	96.4	6	5.6
Sep-22	1134	1089	90.1	95.3	45	5.2
Oct-22	1135	1090	90	94	45	4
Nov-22	1135	1122	90.8	93.4	13	2.6
Dec-22	1142	1129	90	94.2	13	4.2

Fig. 7 (a) Plot of Temp. Vs CRR)

Fig. 7 (b) Plot between Diff. Temp and Diff. CRR

CO₂ reactivity residue (CRR) is influenced by baking temperature. As presented in Table 5 and Fig. 7(a) and 7(b), furnace data has been reorganized, showing CRR values ranging from 84 to 98. This indicates that one anode reached a CRR of 84, another 98, with the remaining anodes falling within this range. A predominance of lower CRR values correlates with diminished quality and adverse carbon performance during electrolysis. CRR fluctuations exhibit a pattern, with larger temperature differentials causing greater CRR disparities. Although various factors contribute, baking temperature remains the most critical. Uneven heating across furnace layers leads to CRR variability, increasing carbon anode consumption during electrolysis [31].

4.5 Temperature and ARR

Table 6 Temperature and ARR

Month	Final Anode Temp (Max)- °C	Final Anode Temp (Minm)- °C	ARR	ARR	Diff. in Temp °C	Diff. in ARR
Nov-21	1137	1092	60.8	72.5	45	11.7
Dec-21	1142	1134	60.9	70.8	8	9.9
Jan-22	1139	1134	64.2	68.7	5	4.5
Feb-22	1137	1112	61	67.6	25	6.6
Mar-22	1142	1132	57.7	68.1	10	10.4
Apr-22	1137	1135	60.2	66.4	2	6.2
May-22	1137	1116	69.5	80	21	10.5

Jun-22	1136	1083	66	77.4	53	11.4
July-22	1131	1128	70.2	77.5	3	7.3
Aug-22	1134	1128	72.7	77.5	6	4.8
Sep-22	1134	1089	67.3	74.7	45	7.4
Oct-22	1135	1090	63.6	77	45	14
Nov-22	1135	1122	66.5	73.3	13	6.8
Dec-22	1142	1129	70	79.7	13	9.7

Fig: 8 (a) Plot between Temperature and ARR

Fig. 8 (b) Plot of Difference in Temperature and Difference in ARR

Air reactivity residue (ARR) is significantly influenced by baking temperature. As presented in Table 6 and Figs. 15 and 16, furnace data is reorganized monthly, emphasizing high and low values rather than averages. ARR ranges from 60.8 to 80, indicating substantial variability, with a notable concentration of anodes exhibiting lower ARR, thereby increasing carbon consumption during electrolysis. ARR fluctuations correlate with temperature differentials—greater temperature variance corresponds to larger ARR discrepancies. Among all factors, baking temperature predominantly governs anode consumption in electrolysis [32]. A high proportion (20–30%) of anodes with low ARR significantly elevates carbon usage, regardless of other stable parameters. Uneven baking across furnace layers contributes to this wide variation. While mean values may suffice for academic analysis, they inadequately reflect industrial performance, potentially masking furnace inefficiencies.

Table 7: Anode Temperature vs. Governing Process Parameters for Anode Quality

4.6 Technical Parameters (Laboratory tests of samples) organized in graphical form:

Sample No.	Anode Temp	Geometrical Density	Electrical Resistivity	Air Reactivity residue	Carboxy Reactivity Residue
1	1090°C	1.591	56.99	80.1	88.9
2	1090°C	1.607	56.93	87.1	89.1
3	1090°C	1.57	56.0	83.2	92
4	1090°C	1.58	54.9	87.7	86.7
5	1090°C	1.58	55.5	83.2	89.3
6	1090°C	1.60	54.5	94.0	85.9
7	1090°C	1.59	55.7	93.9	87.4
8	1090°C	1.58	56.0	92.3	87.5
9	1090°C	1.59	54.5	84.2	85.1
10	1090°C	1.588	59.2	80.0	94.1
11	1090°C	1.587	54.8	80.8	94.0
12	1090°C	1.599	55.5	78.3	94.3
13	1090°C	1.585	54.6	79.9	89.8
14	1090°C	1.584	58.9	78.2	90.1

15	1090°C	1.597	57.7	79.1	93.3
16	1090°C	1.587	59.5	79.0	91.2
17	1090°C	1.596	59.3	78.8	91.8
18	1090°C	1.602	57.1	77.7	93.2
19	1090°C	1.589	56.9	79.1	90.0
20	1090°C	1.579	56.8	79.4	90.2
21	1090°C	1.594	56.5	79.5	91.5

Fig. 9 Plot between no. of samples vs. samples which qualify & samples performed below the limit.

Fig. 10 Plot between no. of samples and samples which qualify & samples performed below the limit

Fig. 11 No of samples vs. samples which qualify & samples performed below the limit.

Fig. 12 No of samples vs. samples which qualify & samples performed below the limit)

Fig. 13 Geometrical density variation

Fig. 14 Electrical resistivity variation

Fig. 15 Air reactivity residue variation

Fig. 16 Plot of Carboxy reactivity residue variation

5.0 Conclusions:

1. Under-baking due to inadequate heat penetration:

If more than 95% of anodes exhibit a bulk density exceeding 1.585 units and a CRR (Carbon Reactivity Ratio) greater than 92%, yet the ARR (Apparent Resistivity Ratio) remains within the range of 65–70%, it suggests that the baking process is insufficient for anode layers located farther from the burners. This underperformance indicates suboptimal heat penetration, leading to under-baked anodes.

2. Uneven Heat Flux Indicated by Temperature Variations:

Significant temperature disparities among anodes (exceeding 10–15°C) despite a stable flue gas temperature imply non-uniform heat flux distribution. Such uneven thermal gradients suggest that a considerable proportion of the anodes are likely under-baked.

3. Indicators of Measurement Error in Temperature Readings:

If anode temperatures exceed the operational limits but one or more critical parameters such as ARR, CRR, electrical resistivity, or bulk density fall below expected values, it indicates potential human error in temperature measurement. This could arise from improper placement of thermal gauges or inaccurate observation, such as recording flue gas temperatures instead of the actual anode temperature.

4. Limitations of Relying Solely on Average Values:

Relying exclusively on average parameter values may obscure significant deviations, potentially masking opportunities for process optimization. A high variance, where some readings are excessively high or low, can distort the interpretation of performance metrics and hinder targeted improvements.

5. Impact of Anode Quality Variability on Electrolysis Efficiency:

The coexistence of severely underperforming and highly efficient anodes can have detrimental effects on electrolysis stability. To mitigate this risk, maintaining a narrow standard deviation across critical parameters is essential. Continuous monitoring should be employed to ensure uniformity in anode quality.

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